

LUST

by

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Lust is a serious issue in the culture today that is invading human sanctity, dignity, and healthy relationships. Lust is the root cause of many serious sins like pornography, fornication, adultery, and homosexual and polygamous relations. It is not only affecting the people in the world but also destroying marriages within the church and the effectiveness of Christian witness and ministry.

A person struggling with lust is often consumed with an obsessive passion for sex and struggles with pornography and masturbation. Lust is sinful because it disregards God's standards for human flourishing.¹ Some of the consequences of lust include compulsive masturbation, addiction to pornography, premarital sex, adultery, multiple affairs, and broken marriages.² Bible condemns both the outward expressions of lust and inward lustful thinking. Jesus pointed out that if a person looks at a woman lustfully, he has already committed adultery in his heart (Matthew 5:27-28). By condemning lust, Jesus addressed the moral root of the problem.³ Those who want to help the folks who are struggling with lust should use a three-step approach to recover them from their sin. First, they should identify the person, empathize with them, and share the gospel with them. Second, they should coach the person to see the seriousness of their sin and assist them to remove the sources and maintain accountability. Third,

¹ Randy C. Alcorn, *Christians in the Wake of the Sexual Revolution: Recovering Our Sexual Sanity* (Portland: Multnomah Press, 1985), 202.

² Stuart Scott, *Biblical Manhood: Masculinity, Leadership and Decision Making* (Bemidji, MN: Focus Publishing, 2009), 81.

³ Alcorn, *Christians in the Wake of the Sexual Revolution*, 203-205.

they should join the person in a good Christian community that comforts the person and encourage them in their walk with the Lord.

Experience of the Problem

A person struggling with lust is often consumed with an obsessive passion that concentrates on some appealing object. The object of lust could be morally neutral, but it becomes a weapon for the sinfulness of lust. Lust is not evil because it is intense, or it has something to do with sex. It is evil because it disregards God's standards for human flourishing. It develops, breeds, and continues in a person's heart and it exercises dominion over a person's heart. Since there is no satisfaction besides God and his good plans for us, there is no joy and fulfillment for a person who is obsessed with lust.⁴

Sources and Circumstances that Contribute to the Issue of Lust (Heat)

A person struggling with lust often struggles with pornography and masturbation. Some of them are well-educated, good professionals, and often active in the church. They often struggle to maintain serious healthy relationships. Not everyone who struggles with lust is considered a "sex addict." Some of them do not watch porn and do not have illegitimate sexual relations. People often struggle with lust have some issues in building intimate relationships. They maintain cordial safe relationships, but not at a deep level. They want to be safe, they often consider their priorities, and they are selfish.⁵

Some of the people who struggle with lust and masturbation had a history of domineering parents and shameful treatment of their sexuality, and traumatic experiences in

⁴ Alcorn, *Christians in the Wake of the Sexual Revolution*, 202.

⁵ John F. Bettler, "When the Problem Is Sexual Sin: A Counseling Model." *The Journal of Biblical Counseling* 13, No. 3 (Spr 1995): 16-18.

childhood. Some people who struggle with multiple affairs have reported that they were raised by wealthy successful divorced parents who did not give them much care. They suspect that their parents are involved in affairs. It makes it difficult for them to trust in marriage. Some people who struggle with uncontrollable urges reported that they are not satisfied in their marriages. They reported that they want more sex than their partner and their partner is not helping them with their desires. These are some of the contributing factors to the issue.⁶

There are three main sources that contribute to the issue of lust: childhood trauma, physiology, and culture. Childhood trauma contributes to the issue along with other sources. Experiences of humiliation, anger, confusion, and anxiety affects a person's sexual identity and sexual desires. When a person is dominated and suppressed by his parents, he or she treats his body with contempt and fear. It would make it difficult for them to integrate their sexual desire in a constructive way. It also results in sexual alienation and depersonalization.⁷ Childhood loss and trauma are certainly a part of a person's struggle. A child who is abandoned by his father or mother has a tendency to see the opposite sex for their fulfilment.

Second, the physiology of a person can contribute to their struggle with lust. Some people are genetically predisposed to have stronger sexual urges than others.⁸ The issue of lust is complex, it involves the body, soul, and heart. Certainly, there is a relationship between sexual desire and biological hormones in one's body. The level of androgenic hormones plays an important role in evoking sexual desire. However, hormones are not the only determining factor

⁶ Ryan LaMothe, "Maddening Desire: Understanding Lust in Pastoral Counseling." *Pastoral Psychology* 54, no. 5 (2006): 479–95.

⁷ LaMothe, 491.

⁸ LaMothe, 491

in whether an individual will or will not feel sexual desire.⁹ Good physical health¹⁰, gender, and usage of drugs also play a role.¹¹

Third, a culture that promotes individual's fulfilment and sexual liberation can contribute to the issue. In the western culture, individual desires are seen as rights to be fulfilled. In the countries like United States, women and men are objectified as sexual objects to promote the advertisements of products. It leads to sexual preoccupation and pseudo intimacy. The rise of pornographic industry influenced the culture and became a major contributor for lust.¹² However, none of the contributing factors should be considered as excuses for a deliberate sexual sin, rather, they should be understood in order to help a person in their struggles.

Some of the contributing factors for the issue include the desires of our heart: anger, self-pity, discontentment, and fear. Sinful anger is a consequence of a covetous thought life of a person.¹³ The response of anger is fuelled by emotional energy due to failed expectations. A person might attempt to console himself by indulging in the sin as a compensation for his/her perceived loss. A self-gratifying sex is one form of many different types of sexual manifestations of sinful anger.¹⁴ A sinful self-pity is the outcome of loss of a perceived right. Self-pity results into the justification for the desire of compensation for the perceived loss. A person who indulges in sexual sin often rationalizes their sin by thinking that they suffered some loss.¹⁵

⁹ Pamela C. Regan and Ellen Berscheid, *Lust: What We Know About Human Sexual Desire* (Thousand Oaks: Sage Publications, 1999), 59.

¹⁰ Regan and Berscheid, 54.

¹¹ Regan and Berscheid, 59.

¹² LaMothe, *Maddening Desire*, 492-493.

¹³ John D. Street. *Passions of the Heart: Biblical Counsel for Stubborn Sexual Sins* (Phillipsburg, New Jersey: P&R Publishing, 2019), 117.

¹⁴ Street, *Passions of the Heart*, 118-119.

¹⁵ Street, 123.

Similarly, unrealized expectations produce discontentment and fear in a person's heart that becomes a fertile ground for lust.¹⁶

Manifestations and Consequences of the Lust (Thorns)

Lust destroys God's design for human sexuality, marital intimacy, and healthy relationships with others. However, there are many people who manage their marriages and professional jobs while being struggling with lust. Not every person has same level of struggle with lust. Irrespective of the intensity of the issue and its visible consequences, it needs to be addressed.

Lustful thinking is serious sin in God's sight. It is an inward sin that has the potential to outgrow and affect us and others. Sexual lust is not usually satisfied until physical erotic desire achieves its fulfilment. The sinful attitude of flesh does not give up until it is satisfied or mortified. If lust is not mortified, it yields into masturbation, internet pornography, premarital sex, sex outside marriage, sex with a child, sex with an animal, and homosexual tendencies. These outward sins are expressions of inward lustful heart.¹⁷

Biblical/Theological Considerations

The word "lust" means to have a strong desire that is focused on attaining what is desired. The word for lust is *epithumia* in Greek. The word was used in two senses: good and bad. In a positive sense, the word was used to denote the good desire. In Luke 22:15, Jesus earnestly desired to eat the Passover with his disciples before he died. In 1 Thessalonians 2:17, Paul had a great desire to see the Thessalonians. In 1 Timothy 3:1, it was considered as a good

¹⁶ Street, 135,140.

¹⁷ Scott, Biblical Manhood, 81.

desire if someone likes to pursue the office of overseer. In a negative sense, the word *epithumia* was understood as “evil desire” or “lust.”¹⁸

The issue of lust is addressed comprehensively in the scriptures. Randy C. Alcorn pointed out that sexual lust is denounced in the Hebrew scriptures. In Exodus 20:17, one of the ten commandments prohibited adultery and covetousness. In the wisdom literature, the authors warned the covenant community against lust and immorality (Proverbs 2:16-19). The stories of Samson, David, and Hosea educated us to hate immorality and adultery as it is displeasing to the Lord.¹⁹

In the New Testament, the issue was addressed at the heart level. The inward lust was considered a serious sin. Jesus did not only condemn adultery, but he also raised the standards for purity. He pointed out that if a person looks at a woman lustfully, he has already committed adultery in his heart (Matthew 5:27-28). By condemning lust, he addressed the moral root of the problem and prevented excuses to fall into sin. The issue of lust is considered a sinful principle in the flesh, it is part of the sinful nature of man that rebels against God (Romans 7:4-25, Galatians 5:13-26).²⁰

Biblical Exegesis

Exodus 20:14. The Sinai covenant demands Israelites to obey God by not committing adultery. The Hebrew word *naaph* refers to adultery. It is specifically concerning to a sexual relationship with a person in violation of their marital commitment. It should be noted that betrothal is considered as a legal binding in the Hebrew culture and any sexual relationship

¹⁸ Scott, 80.

¹⁹ Alcorn, *Christians in the Wake of the Sexual Revolution*, 202-203.

²⁰ Alcorn, *Christians in the Wake of the Sexual Revolution*, 203-205.

outside of betrothal is considered as adultery. The word *naaph* is also used as a metaphor to describe idolatry.²¹

The act of adultery is explicitly prohibited in the ten commandments because of its necessity. Duane A. Garrett clarified that marriage is considered a foundational aspect of the survival of families in a culture. However, other forms of immorality including premarital sex and homosexuality were equally sinful and were condemned. For example, sexual relationship before marriage was also condemned in the law (Leviticus 21:9).²²

Matthew 5:27-30. In contrast to the Old Testament commandments, the issue of lust was addressed at the heart level. Jesus condemned the thoughts of lust and adultery, not just the actions. David L Turner argued that the thoughts of lust were not addressed in the Old Testament and Second Temple Judaism. He pointed out that Jesus maintained a rigorous sexual ethic by condemning lustful thoughts as adultery. The condemnation of lustful thoughts suggests that Jesus interpreted the seventh commandment (prohibiting adultery) in light of the tenth commandment (prohibition of covetousness). Carson pointed out that Matthew 5:28 does not necessarily about looking with lust, but it is looking with lust to entice her.²³

In order to prohibit adultery and sexual immorality, one has to take radical steps. Jesus demanded radical obedience using the hyperbole of cutting one's own eye or right hand. However, its seriousness should not be undermined. Sin must be avoided at any cost. This is a

²¹ Garrett, Duane A. *A Commentary on Exodus*. Kregel Exegetical Library (Grand Rapids: Kregel Academic, 2014), 481.

²² Garrett, *A Commentary on Exodus*, 481.

²³ Craig S. Keener, *A Commentary on the Gospel of Matthew* (Grand Rapids, MI: W.B. Eerdmans Pub), 1999, 170.

serious sin that endangers a person's final destiny. It is better to deal with lust decisively than to be thrown into the hell.²⁴

Romans 1:24-27. In this passage, Paul explained God's wrath on the people who disregard him and his moral stipulations. God gave them up to their lustful impurity and dishonoring of their own bodies. They were given up because they were already indulged themselves in sin. This moral damnation of people by God was due to their willful rebellion against God and their idolatry. The root cause of rampant sexual immorality is identified as their adherence to idols. This led to their moral failure and resulted in homosexual affairs which are contrary to nature. This is considered a grievous sin in God's sight and in the sight of people according to their cultural norms. Homosexuality among males and females is considered a departure from nature. He also condemned that those who practice such practices suffer the eternal wrath of God.²⁵

Romans 8:5-8. In this passage, Paul addressed the issue of the battle between the sinful nature of the flesh and the work of the Spirit. He elaborated the weakness of the flesh. The sinful nature of the flesh is hostile to God, and it leads to death. The mindset produced by the sinful flesh does not submit to God's law.²⁶ In this passage, Paul did not address the issue of lust directly. However, it is understood that the issue of lust is typically a problem of our sinful nature in the flesh. The struggle with lust is not only a problem for unbelievers but also a major challenge for Christians.

²⁴ Keener, *A Commentary on the Gospel of Matthew*, 170-171.

²⁵ Douglas J. Moo, *The Epistle to the Romans*. The New International Commentary on the New Testament (Grand Rapids, MI: Eerdmans, 1996), 120-126.

²⁶ Moo, *The Epistle to the Romans*, 510-512.

1 Corinthians 6:9-11. In this passage, Paul exhorted Christians to flee from sexual immorality, adultery, idolatry, homosexuality, drunkenness, and robbery. He clarified that those who practice such evil practices do not inherit the kingdom of God. The Greek word for sexual immorality is “*pornoi*” in this passage and it covers a range of sexual sins.

Paul pointed out that the people who live a lifestyle of sin are not incompatible with the kingdom of God. The term “adulterer” applies to people who have sexual relationships outside of marriage. He also condemned the practice of homosexuality. Paul used two words (*malakoi* and *arsenokoitai*) to denounce the practices of active and passive homosexual practices. If a person is continued to live in such grievous sins should not deceive themselves that they are in God’s covenant community.²⁷ He also assured God’s grace for the people who have repented from those sins. He assured the people who put their trust in Christ are washed, sanctified, and justified by the grace of God and through the work of the Spirit. This has changed their identity from sinners to saints in Christ.²⁸

James 1:13-15. In this passage, James corrected the understanding of some Christians who charge God with the responsibility of sin. He pointed out that no sin or temptation comes from God.²⁹ The desire for sin is inherent for humans as he is a fallen being. He is apt to be sinful. Each man commits sin and is enticed by it by his own lust. There is also a progression of sin from its conception to its ultimate consequence of death.³⁰

²⁷ Paul Gardner, *1 Corinthians*, Zondervan Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament, vol. 7 (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2018), 261-262.

²⁸ Gardner, *1 Corinthians*, 262-263.

²⁹ James B. Adamson, *The Epistle of James*, The New International Commentary on the New Testament (Grand Rapids, MI: W.B. Eerdmans Pub, 1976), 69-70.

³⁰ Adamson, *The Epistle of James*, 71-72.

Freedom from Lust (Fruit)

It is possible to have victory over the sin of lust. A person who is freed from the bondage of lust and its manifestations is recognized by their repentance from sin (Psalm 51), their security in Christ (John 3:16, Romans 3:23), and the fruit of the Spirit (Galatians 5:22-23). In contrary to the work of the flesh, the fruit of the Spirit shows God's gracious work in a person's heart. Although a person is never completely free from sin in this world, it is possible live faithfully by the grace of God (Romans 12:1-2). The person also bears much fruit in his life. The fruit of the Spirit is love, joy, peace, patience, kindness, goodness, faithfulness, gentleness, and self-control. The people who belong to Christ have crucified the flesh with its passions and desires (Galatians, 22-24, ESV).

In the new covenant ethics, love is central to Christian faith. A Christian who is freed from lust is filled with joy and comfort from God because he received God's love. He enjoys peace with God. He patiently waits for God and show kindness to others. He is generous to others. He trusts God and other people in his life. He exercises patience and gentleness. These are key markers of his new identity in Christ and the evidence of transformation.³¹

Speaking the Gospel (Cross)

God loved the sinners and sent his only begotten Son for the redemption of sinners (John 3:16, Romans 5:8). The finished work of Christ is sufficient to heal a person from their wounds of his and redeem him from the bondage of sin. The message of the gospel needs to be applied to the suffering sinners. I would like to apply a three-step approach to recover a person from the bondage of lust and its manifestations. First, I would like to identify the person and empathize with him/her for his struggle with sin and the damage that has been caused to himself,

³¹ Douglas J. Moo, *Galatians*. Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament (Baker Academic, 2013), 364-366.

his family, and others. I also would like to share the gospel with them and show them the need for their repentance, and God's grace and his provisions for them. Second, I would like to coach the person and help them to see the seriousness of their sin and assist them to remove the sources and maintain accountability. Third, I would like to encourage him to be a part of the community that believes in the gospel, preaches God's word faithfully, comfort him and encourage him in his walk with the Lord.

First, the person who is struggling with lust needs to be identified and exposed to the gospel of Jesus Christ. If we preach our sermons legalistically and live a life of self-righteousness or licentiousness, it drives people away from the grace of God. We need to preach the gospel faithfully and reach out to the people who are struggling with sin. The people who are struggling with lust should understand that God is loving them. God's love is powerful enough to convince a sinner of their sin against loving and just God. As I counsel this person, I encourage him that God loves him in spite of his situation and that Christ died for him while he was still a sinner. I also warn him of the eternal consequences of his sin, and I exhort him to confess his sin and turn to Christ (Romans 3:23, 5:28).

In the second step, I would like to coach them to fight against sin by encouraging them to confess their sins on daily basis and providing them resources, online filters, and accountability partners and groups. I encourage them to write down the list of idols in their life.³² I encourage them to write down the list of places, accessories, and people in their life that are causing him to sin against God. I encourage him to avoid the access points to sin. I also would like to encourage them to confess his sins specifically on daily basis.³³ If they were a new believer, I would teach them how to read the Bible and pray to God by himself. If they are

³² John D. Street, *Men Counseling Men* (Eugene, Or: Harvest House, 2013), 301.

³³ Street, 302.

already a believer, I encourage him to read God’s word faithfully and apply it to his life. I also provide with him some good resources on Christian discipleship and purity. I assist him to find online filters like covenant eyes to avoid the temptation. I encourage him to find a trustworthy accountability partner to confess his sin and share his struggles. A faithful accountability partnership is characterized by open clean conversations, maturity, seriousness, and perseverance.³⁴

In the third step, I help the person to join a Bible-believing church and a good community that is willing to walk alongside him in his path to sanctification. A good Christian community comforts him and encourages him in his personal life. It helps him to grow in his walk with the Lord. It heals him from his wounds, and it helps him to strive toward faithful Christian life.

³⁴ Lambert, Heath. *Finally Free: Fighting for Purity with the Power of Grace* (Grand Rapids, MI: Zondervan, 2013), 56.

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